

Title: Applying Quantitative Benefit-Risk Analysis to Support Portfolio Prioritization Decisions

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I. Introduction

Recently, attention has been given to the role of quantitative benefit-risk Assessment (qBRA) in supporting regulator decisions [1, 2, 3], and examples of regulatory use of qBRA have been published [4]. Reviews have also identified sponsors using qBRA to support internal decision-making [5]. Given this and the challenges facing internal decision-making (i.e., multi-dimensional characteristics of treatments, considerations of trade-offs between multiple endpoints, divergent priorities among internal stakeholders, dealing with uncertainty in the performance of molecule combinations, and uncertainty in the trade-offs), sponsors can optimize their chances of achieving regulatory success by integrating the insights of qBRA earlier in their decision-making process. However, few examples of sponsors' internal use of qBRA have been published, probably due to the proprietary nature of such work. Also, there is little guidance or published case studies to support sponsors in this endeavor.

This commentary reports on applying qBRA to support sponsor go/no-go decision-making at the end of phase 2. We describe the pilot of the qBRA in evaluating two hypothetical drugs for treating diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL).

II. Illustration

Table 1 summarizes the application of qBRA to support the evaluation of two hypothetical drugs for treating diffuse DLBCL. qBRA applies a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) framework [6] to bring formal analytical methods to support benefit-risk decisions. The key MCDA steps involve (i) defining the decision problem, (ii) defining the criteria relevant to the decision problem and the value framework that identifies how they contribute to the decision, (iii) measuring performance against criteria, (iv) eliciting preferences for criteria and (v) constructing an aggregation model that combines criteria performance and weights in a manner consistent with the value framework, as well as exploring the impact of uncertainty in model inputs [6].

A range of internal experts (i.e., from the Drug Development Team (DDT)) generated attributes and population of performance and preference data required in the evaluation framework. The DDT members agreed on the criteria to be used (Table, Step 2) and provided scores and weights of these criteria during facilitated workshop sessions (Table, Steps 3-5). Biostatisticians were engaged to re-analyze trial data to estimate the performance, including 95% confidence intervals of molecules against criteria. It is important to anticipate this step, as criteria will only sometimes align with clinical study endpoints. Variation between criteria and trial endpoints can result from, for instance, avoiding overlap in the concepts captured by criteria.

The criteria selection was challenging due to the complexity and multi-faceted nature of the disease area and the different ways of measuring the endpoints. Several iterations are required between steps 1 and 2 of the MCDA to construct a sound set of criteria with the desired properties [7], including ensuring adequate performance data.

Two oncologists from the DDT applied their expertise to supply the subjective trade-offs using the swing weighting method (SW) [8, 9] to derive the MCDA weights. These trade-offs are typically not stated explicitly but instead implied by statements about the acceptability, or not, of a set of benefits and risks of a drug. Weights are then combined with the performance of the drug and alternative on each outcome and summed to produce the total value of each alternative (Table, step 6). An alternative with the best possible performance on each outcome would have a total value of 1, and an alternative with the worst possible performance would have a value of 0.

Visual representations of the aggregated and the probabilistic sensitivity analyses (PSA) results were used in the drug development team's (DDT) meeting to facilitate discussion surrounding the results (Table, Step 7). The visual translations of the quantitative insight enabled the team to have a shared understanding of the results and generate insight more effectively. The display further supported reaching an agreement by highlighting areas of critical disagreement that needed further exploration to determine a rationale for choosing between the molecules (Table, Step 8).

As well as informing decisions to move assets into Phase 3, the MCDA can help identify the value of further evidence to support the qBRA. For example, when committee members display important differences in criteria weights, this might suggest further patient preference data collection to support approval and reimbursement decisions. In this case, a study of patient preferences can be undertaken alongside the Phase 3 trial to prepare for regulatory submission.

The MCDA framework can inform how changes in trial design impact the assessment of the benefits and risks of assets. The relative value of changes in endpoints can inform the selection of endpoints in future Phase 3 trials. The framework can also reveal how reducing the uncertainty around performance inputs will impact the likelihood that an asset has a positive benefit-risk balance, which can inform assessments of the value of increasing the sample size of the Phase 3 trial.

Table 1: MCDA for evaluating molecules to treat patients with DLBCL

MCDA Step & Description	Applications, Lessons Learnt & Recommendations
<p>1. Defining the decision problem</p> <p>Agree on a shared definition of the problem, select molecules to be evaluated, and determine the required outputs and stakeholders involved.</p>	<p>Support the choice of which molecules in the pipelines to progress from PII to PIII and improve the probability of making the right choice.</p> <p>Application in DLBCL, between 2 hypothetical molecules for illustration.</p> <p>The DDT included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Committee members familiar with the disease (oncologists with expertise in treating patients with DLBCL) ● Biostatisticians ● Committee members familiar with the trial designs for the molecules of interest and the profile of competitor products; and regulators' payers' concerns. ● Representatives of internal stakeholders on the DDT

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<p>2. Selecting and structuring criteria</p> <p>Identify criteria relevant for evaluating the molecules, ensuring they meet the properties for an additive aggregation (see Marsh et al., 2016 for more details on properties).</p>	<p>Benefit endpoints: Disease Progression, Response (not sustained), Sustained-Response</p> <p>Risk endpoints: Fatal AEs, SAEs (excluding septic shock), AEs leading to withdrawal (excluding septic shock or IRR), Grade 3-4 AEs (excluding septic shock or IRR), Septic shock, IRR</p> <p>Challenges encountered:</p> <p>Availability of data, selecting a manageable set of criteria, ensuring the requirements had desired properties (preference independence and non-overlap). This required restructuring specific criteria and evaluating whether it would be possible to estimate the performance of these newly defined criteria.</p>																																																						
<p>3. Measuring performance</p> <p>Gather performance data on the molecules for each criterion, including uncertainty</p>	<p>Incidence rates (95% CI) of outcomes at one year:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="817 544 1591 1021"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Outcomes at 1 year</th> <th>Min</th> <th>Max</th> <th>Drug A (n=703) (mean, LCI-UCI)</th> <th>Drug B (n=704) (mean, LCI-UCI)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="3">EFFICACY</td> <td>Response sustained</td> <td>60%</td> <td>72%</td> <td>72.0% (68.56-75.19)</td> <td>67.5% (63.94-70.85)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Response not sustained</td> <td>2%</td> <td>8%</td> <td>6.0% (4.47-8.00)</td> <td>7.7% (5.95-9.91)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Progressed</td> <td>10%</td> <td>20%</td> <td>13.3% (10.99-16.01)</td> <td>11.5% (9.35-14.07)</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="7">RISKS</td> <td>Fatal AE</td> <td>4%</td> <td>7%</td> <td>5.5% (4.04-7.44)</td> <td>4.0% (2.78-5.71)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SAE</td> <td>30%</td> <td>36%</td> <td>33.0% (29.62-36.56)</td> <td>32.9% (29.52-36.46)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>AEs leading to withdrawal - other than septic shock or IRR</td> <td>1%</td> <td>10%</td> <td>6.0% (4.47-8.00)</td> <td>4.0% (2.78-5.71)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Grade 3-4 AEs – other than septic shock or IRR</td> <td>60%</td> <td>72%</td> <td>64.0% (60.38-67.46)</td> <td>62.0% (58.35-65.51)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Septic shock</td> <td>0%</td> <td>4%</td> <td>2.0% (1.20-3.32)</td> <td>2.1% (1.27-3.44)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>IRR</td> <td>3%</td> <td>12%</td> <td>5.1% (3.70-6.98)</td> <td>5.0% (3.62-6.87)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Colors reflect the difference in performances: green: better performance, orange: poorer performance, no color: similar performance.</p>			Outcomes at 1 year	Min	Max	Drug A (n=703) (mean, LCI-UCI)	Drug B (n=704) (mean, LCI-UCI)	EFFICACY	Response sustained	60%	72%	72.0% (68.56-75.19)	67.5% (63.94-70.85)	Response not sustained	2%	8%	6.0% (4.47-8.00)	7.7% (5.95-9.91)	Progressed	10%	20%	13.3% (10.99-16.01)	11.5% (9.35-14.07)	RISKS	Fatal AE	4%	7%	5.5% (4.04-7.44)	4.0% (2.78-5.71)	SAE	30%	36%	33.0% (29.62-36.56)	32.9% (29.52-36.46)	AEs leading to withdrawal - other than septic shock or IRR	1%	10%	6.0% (4.47-8.00)	4.0% (2.78-5.71)	Grade 3-4 AEs – other than septic shock or IRR	60%	72%	64.0% (60.38-67.46)	62.0% (58.35-65.51)	Septic shock	0%	4%	2.0% (1.20-3.32)	2.1% (1.27-3.44)	IRR	3%	12%	5.1% (3.70-6.98)	5.0% (3.62-6.87)
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	<p>4. Scoring alternatives</p> <p>Elicitation of stakeholders' preferences within criteria and consistency checks</p>	<p>We used a two-step approach to elicit the scoring of outcomes within criteria and checked linearity (e.g., whether each additional fatality or each newly responding patient is valued equally). A single breakpoint was evaluated using the bisection method if it was not valued equally. For criteria with narrow ranges of performance, stakeholders assumed linearity. For those with more extensive ranges, we applied piecewise value functions..</p>																																																					
<p>5. Weighting criteria</p> <p>Elicitation of stakeholders' preferences/priorities between criteria and consistency checks</p>	<p>Weighting the performance of each asset by the key stakeholders allows a comparison of the overall value of assets on a single standard scale. We used the swing weighting method to elicit the weights/priorities among the criteria. Weights are a numerical representation of subjective values and thus can be challenging for stakeholders to provide. We presented Committee members with the marginal rates of substitution between criteria implied by the weights they provided. They were allowed to revisit their weight estimates until they generated a marginal rate of substitution they were satisfied with.</p> <p>Two committee members contributed weights. Preferences were heterogeneous. One of the oncologists put more weight on improving 'Response-Sustained' and reducing 'Grade 3-4 AEs'. The other oncologist put more weight on reducing 'Fatal AEs' and 'AEs leading to withdrawal.' Preferences for the other endpoints are relatively similar (Figure 1).</p>																																																						

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	<p>Figure 1: Normalized weights for the two stakeholders (DM1=oncologist 1; DM2=Oncologist 2)</p>
<p>6. Calculating aggregate scores</p> <p>Using an additive function to aggregate the scores and weights and obtain an overall value of the molecules.</p>	<p>The assessment of the molecules was sensitive to the variation weights provided by the two committee members (Figure 2). The source of this difference was the weight attached to “Sustained-Response,” “Fatal AEs,” and “Grade 3-4 AEs”.</p> <p>Figure 2: Overall value for the two stakeholders</p>
<p>7. Dealing with uncertainty</p> <p>Exploring the impact of uncertainty around performance estimates to evaluate the benefit-risk balance of molecules.</p>	<p>Given the uncertainty in model inputs, the evaluation was run probabilistically to assess the likelihood that one therapy is preferred to another, given the uncertainty of the performance estimates.</p> <p>The output from the probabilistic running of the evaluation was a scatter plot on a benefit-risk plane (Figure 3). Both molecules had a positive B-R balance. Committee Member 1 viewed the B-R profile of both drugs more positively than Committee Member 2.</p> <p>Figure 4: Probabilistic Sensitivity Analysis: Rank Probability Output for Two Stakeholders</p>

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<p data-bbox="193 232 794 266">8. Reporting and interpretation</p> <p data-bbox="193 300 794 356">Interpretation of the MCDA outputs, sensitivity analyses, and evaluation of implications for decision-making</p>	<p data-bbox="799 232 1591 412">Results show that the benefit-risk is sensitive to individual committee member weights for outcomes, particularly the preference for “Response-Sustained” and “Grade 3-4 AEs”, and on reducing ‘Fatal AEs’ and ‘AEs leading to withdrawal. Identifying that committee member weights produce divergent decisions and which of their weights drive this divergence is an important starting point for committee deliberation to conclude. If committee members cannot align on weights, collecting patient or regulator preferences for endpoints may provide additional value to this analysis.</p>

III. Conclusions

This paper reports on a case study of applying qBRA to support sponsors' internal decisions of determining the best combination therapy to advance from Phase 2 to Phase 3. Specifically, a qBRA based on MCDA was designed to support committees to evaluate assets for progression to Phase 3. It provides a structured approach to assessing the likelihood that assets will achieve a clinical probability of successfully transitioning to the next phase and meet efficacy and safety requirements. This development of this framework was motivated by recent developments in healthcare decision-making, namely the increasing use of structured decision support to improve the quality of decision-making and the increasing use of qBRA by regulators.

The qBRA supports DDTs to increase the probability that the right assets are progressed to Phase 3 by (i) ensuring completeness, considering all relevant criteria; (ii) enabling formal incorporation of value judgments by quantifying the value judgments in an organized and robust way, and by combining this information with performance measurement; (iii) fostering a shared understanding of a decision problem; (iv) enriching discussions by identifying areas of important disagreement, enriching discussions; (v) enabling transparency in decision-making by forming a transparent link between judgments and decisions; and (vi) generating action by providing accessible visual insight accessible to audiences with diverse technical backgrounds. The qBRA is especially useful during Phase 2 when the endpoints available for the analysis are known. Still, a structured framework is required to handle diverging internal stakeholder priorities and uncertainty in performance estimates, given the limited data available to discern dominant molecules at this stage of development.

The visual translations of the quantitative insight enabled the team to have a shared understanding of the results and generate insight more effectively. The display further supported reaching an agreement by highlighting areas of critical disagreement that needed further exploration to determine a rationale for choosing between the molecules.

As well as informing decisions to move assets into Phase 3, the MCDA can help identify the value of further evidence to support the qBRA. For example, when committee members display essential differences in criteria weights, this might suggest further patient preference data collection to support approval and reimbursement decisions. In this case, a study of patient preferences can be undertaken alongside the Phase 3 trial to prepare for regulatory submission.

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performance inputs will impact the likelihood that an asset has a positive benefit-risk balance, which can inform assessments of the value of increasing the sample size of the Phase 3 trial.

The MCDA can support decision-making when decisions are preference-sensitive, for instance, when: (1) It is not clear whether an asset's benefits exceed its risks; (2) There is expected to be heterogeneity in judgments about the relative importance of evaluation criteria (3) When multiple assets are available, and the task of differentiating them using multiple criteria is complicated.

Overall, the participants felt that formalizing the evaluation of the treatments to enable a comparison of the benefits offered by the drugs and the associated toxicity was beneficial to supporting the decision of which drug to transition to Phase 3. Participants found that the framework enabled them to think critically and objectively through all the criteria. However, it is worth noting some limitations and lessons to take forward in the future development of such frameworks. It is important to remember the iterative process required in identifying the criteria and the population of performance data at this stage, which can be lengthy. Furthermore, it is critical to have support from biostatistical analyses to support the re-analyses of trial data to provide performance estimates for the criteria selected. Providing trade-offs for the criteria was perceived to be challenging by the committee members, given the nature of the tasks and the importance of what was being asked. Thus, an exploration of alternative methods to ease the elicitation of weights and an exploration of weight sensitivity is recommended to facilitate the participation of stakeholders in a live setting. Finally, the qBRA was not tested in an actual decision context, and given the success of this case, future developments should evaluate its use during an actual DDT meeting.

Declarations

Funding: Genentech Inc. paid for the research presented in this paper. All work was conducted by the authors listed.

Conflict of interest: George Quartey and Vidya Maiya are employees of Genentech Inc. during the study. Sumitra Sri-Bhashyam and Kevin Marsh were employees of Evidera, London, UK, during the study.

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to the design of the study. George Quartey, Sumitra Sri-Bhashyam, and Kevin Marsh were involved in analyzing data for the work. All authors were involved in the interpretation of the results. All authors drafted, reviewed, and approved the final manuscript.

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